

Evaluation of Associated factors in Chronic Kidney Disease in Patients with Renal problems.

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Abstract:

Objective: The main objective of this study was to evaluate the associated factors in chronic kidney disease in patients with renal problems.

Type of Study: Cross Sectional.

Place and Duration of Study: This study was carried out in a duration of 10 months from February 2019 to November 2019 in Services Hospital Lahore.

Materials and Methods: A total of 200 patients were selected for the study who were willing to take part in it. The patients visiting the outdoor department of Nephrology or were admitted in ward were seen. Proper sampling technique was used to select the patient. A carefully designed proforma was used to collect the data by interview method and also by secondary data.

Results: A total of 200 patients were selected from medical wards, OPD, kidney transplant OPD and dialysis center. Mean age of the patients was 43.95 years. Evaluation of demographic data shows following results regarding age, marital status, sex and educational status.

Conclusion: The stage 5 or end stage renal disease associated with high morbidity and mortality can be prevented by controlling high blood pressure which can lead to end stage renal disease. The results obtained by this study would have been more accurate if current level of creatinine would have been used. Furthermore, patients were unable to fill some of the questions which affected the results of this study.

Keywords : Chronic Kidney Disease, Kidney Disease

Introduction: Increasing incidence of chronic kidney disease all over the world in recent years along with increased morbidity and mortality has led to increased research on this disease among the health professionals. Cardiovascular diseases which are epidemic in our society are a major risk factor for chronic kidney diseases leading to increased hospitalization and high burden on the economy.

Around 91,314 patients in Brazil were on dialysis in year 2011. In our country, low number of patients are seen on kidney replacement as

compared to developed countries. The main reason behind this is the decreased providence of health facilities to our people. Another reason could be that there is low registration by the dialysis centers. Around 50-70% Brazilians suffering from chronic renal disease die without receiving any kind of treatment.

In Brazil patients suffering from chronic renal failure has have very low access to the data on morbidity and mortality about dialysis population. Chronic kidney disease usually leads to kidney failure resulting in dialysis of transplantation. Chronic renal disease has a significant association with the cardiovascular diseases and it is proposed that people suffering from both are most likely to die from cardiovascular disease. Stage 5 CKD or end stage renal disease is also termed as kidney failure. The last resort for the people with stage 5 renal disease is either transplantation or routine dialysis. It is a major problem all over the world. Worldwide existence of CKD of unknown origin was 1st seen in 1990 and over the last one and half decade its number has risen significantly. The distinctive feature of this disease is that no relation of this disease has been seen with common risk factors like hypertension, DM and chronic glomerulonephritis. Patient is usually asymptomatic in the beginning and by the time one knows about the disease and takes treatment for it, irreversible damage to the kidneys have occurred. End stage renal disease or stage 5 CKD is the point at which kidneys fail to function properly and transplantation or routine dialysis becomes necessary.

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Variables	Frequency	COR (95% CI)	AOR (95% CI)	P-value
Age				
	73	1.00	1.00	1.00
18-28	137	1.29 (0.95, 1.75)	1.46 (1.05, 2.03)	0.02
29-38	50	1.62 (1.08, 2.43)	1.50 (0.95, 2.36)	0.08
39-48	57	2.11 (1.44, 3.09)	2.40 (1.59, 3.65)	0.01
49-58	59	0.91 (0.62, 1.32)	0.77 (0.49, 1.23)	0.28
59-68	38	1.02 (0.67, 1.56)	1.40 (0.85, 2.32)	0.19
>68	8	2.89(1.29,6.45)	3.16 (1.36, 7.35)	0.07
Sex				
Female	191	1.00	1.00	0.01
Male	231	1.52 (0.55, 0.84)	0.62 (0.50, 0.78)	
History of HTN				
No	69	1.00		0.08
Yes	353	0.78 (0.60, 1.02)	1.26 (0.97, 1.64)	
History of DM				
No	345	1.00	1.00	0.03
Yes	77	1.16 (0.94, 1.43)	0.70 (0.51, 0.96)	
History of cigarette smoking				
No	349	1.00	1.00	0.75
Yes	73	0.81 (0.62, 1.07)	1.05 (0.76, 1.45)	
History of non-steroid anti-inflammatory medicine				
No	170	1.00	1.00	0.01
Yes	252	0.65 (0.53, 0.81)	0.48 (0.37, 0.61)	
Habitual of prescribed medication				
No	75	1.00	1.00	0.01
Yes	347	1.73 (1.32, 2.27)	2.22 (1.65, 2.98)	
History of renal stone				
No	346	1.00	1.00	0.79
Yes	76	1.76 (1.34, 2.31)		

Almost all the patients complained that they had to wait for a long duration of period to get the time for dialysis. Data related to the CKD of the patients and history of hypertension, DM and cardiovascular diseases among the patients and adjusted ratio of the factors related to CKD has been shown below:

Discussion: The huge difference of prevalence in patients with stage 1 CRD can be clarified by the difference in micro albuminuria seen among Mexican Americans and non-Hispanic blacks. Using the proper equations, prevalence of CRD has been discovered to be 38.6%. 27.2% is the prevalence of stage 1 and 2 with stage one having

15.6% while stage 2 11.6%. In stage 3 and 4 the prevalence has been found to be 34.1% with stage 3 having 19.4% and stage 4 of 14.7%. Despite the fact that there is less difference among prevalence, CKD EPI underrates the prevalence in comparison with Cockcroft Gault. A study conducted in Canada showed that 80% patients had glomerular filtration rate of 30-60% which is stage three CKD. These results are comparable to our research. Population and the study method can explain the difference between these two studies. Using the Cockcroft Gault equation, study conducted in Tanzania showed the prevalence of CKD among diabetics to be 24.7%. In their study, only incidence of diabetes was used in relation with

CKD which is the reason for high difference between these two studies. Using Cockcroft and MDRD equation prevalence of CRD was found to be 23.8% and 18.8% in the researches carried out in Ethiopia.

Conclusion: The stage 5 or end stage renal disease associated with high morbidity and mortality can be prevented by controlling high blood pressure which can lead to end stage renal disease. The results obtained by this study would have been more accurate if current level of creatinine would have been used. Furthermore, patients were unable to fill some of the questions which affected the results of this study.

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